
Research

Blockchain effects in Latin America and the Caribbean trade, A Gravity Model approach

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Abstract: In international trade, the effect of non-tariff barriers has been widely studied, and several proposed solutions have been given either to reduce these types of barriers and its effects. A revolutionary new technology arises with the potential to propose innovative methods in facilitating trade and reducing or removing significantly trade barriers; this technology is called Blockchain or Distributed Ledger Technology. This research proposes a set of variables based on specific trade facilitation indicators that are directly relevant to the potential of the Blockchain technology and performs an econometrical analysis founded on the Gravity Model to study the explanatory significance and potential effects of these variables in the case of Latin America and the Caribbean with the rest of the world. The results suggest a significant relationship between most of the proposed trade facilitation variables with trade volumes in bilateral trade; indicating, therefore, the potential Blockchain technology could have in boosting international trade.

Keywords: Blockchain, DLT, Gravity Model, Latin America and the Caribbean, non-tariff barriers.

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Introduction

The world is incessantly changing and evolving, driven by technological innovations that influence how we live and do business. Thus, the world economy's history is intimately related to technological progress. For instance, the creation of the steam engine led to mechanized production, the discovery of electricity permitted mass production, and the expansion of the Internet made it possible to coordinate many production stages from afar, leading to a division of production that gave birth to global value chains.

Nevertheless, while information and communication technologies have intensely affected production organizations, they have not digitalized trade transactions, which remain very inefficient to today's standards. In spite of recent efforts to implement electronic processes to manage some aspects of international trade procedures, such as single electronic windows, the transactions remain severely reliant on paper. For instance, a shipment of roses from Kenya to Rotterdam can generate a pile of paper 25 cm high, and the cost of handling it can be higher than the cost of moving the containers (Allison, 2016).

Security concerns and the difficulty of coordinating data flows across borders and between the multiple parties involved in supply chains have hampered efforts to digitalize trade. However, a new technology, Blockchain, is seen as a possible game-changer. However, what is Blockchain, and what is the potential of this technology for international trade? This study will attempt to contribute to shed some light on these questions.

A Blockchain system implies a digital record of transactions –or ledger – that is decentralized (no sole entity controls the network) and distributed (records are shared with all users). Transactions are kept in a very secure, verifiable and permanent manner method using various cryptographic techniques. It is a nonstop increasing list of records, which are combined in "blocks" that are then "chained" to each other using cryptography – henceforth the term "blockchain". As transactions are shared, verified and validated on a peer-to-peer basis, Blockchains can function without the necessity for a central authority or trusted intermediaries. Once input to a blockchain, information is time-stamped and cannot easily be modified. Blockchain, therefore, enables the creation of a shared, trusted ledger that all users can access and check at any moment but that no single party can control. As *The Economist* (2015) calls it, Blockchain is a "trust machine"¹. Because of various cryptographic techniques and their decentralized and distributed nature, blockchains are highly resilient.

In the beginning developed as the technology supporting the digital currency Bitcoin, Blockchain systems soon began to spread beyond cryptocurrencies. The transparent, secure and immutable nature of Blockchain has drawn the interest of both the private sector and government authorities. As an outcome, the quantity of proofs of concepts and pilot projects is rising steeply, and applications cover all sectors of the society and economy. These applications go from finance to e-commerce, food safety, supply-chain management and even voting, with several of these technologies' applications being "permissioned" blockchains that need authorization to perform on the ledger. As a result, billions of funding dollars are invested in blockchain companies, and blockchain-related patents are on the upsurge. Funding from venture capitalists for Blockchain startups has grown progressively and reached US\$ 1 billion in 2017 (CB Insights, 2018), and the rate of blockchain patent applications triplicated that year (Noonan, 2018).

Some motives that make international trade a likely area of high earning for Blockchain employment include the well-known fact that international trade, specifically trade finance and customs, has very intricated network structure with numerous stakeholders, time-consuming processes, trouble and risk in transfer of documents, necessity for information sharing between the parties, and trust issues between parties. In addition, research shows that the number of Blockchain technology usage per industry is highest in the supply chain industry, constituting 19 of all distributed ledger technology (DLT) implementations globally (HFS Research, 2020). Yet, the number and variety of Proof of Concept is still limited, while much potential remains to be met.

Theoretically, the relevance of Blockchain applications is mainly based on non-tariff trade barriers, which are well known to be one of the main factors associated with trade costs². The Latin American and the Caribbean (LAC) countries are under strong effects from non-tariff barriers (NTBs), as the most outstanding example, the Caribbean countries NTBs' impact increased from 95.4 percent (2000) to 128.6 percent (2015) (WTO, 2015). Furthermore, the NTBs are also linked to a greater negative impact on trade than tariff trade barriers, which reflects that they can reduce trade gains that were

¹ <https://www.economist.com/leaders/2015/10/31/the-trust-machine>.

² A 2015 WTO study found that trade costs can amount to a 134 percent ad valorem tariff on a product in high-income countries and to a 219 percent tariff in developing countries (WTO, 2015).

expected from reduction or a cut on tariffs in the first place (Allende Lopez, Alleyne, Giles Alvarez, Khadan, & Waithe, 2020).

Important areas of NTB's are highly related to the potential applications of distributed ledger technology offered by a Blockchain system, hence this research has the motive to analyze the links between NTBs highly related indicators with standard Blockchain functions in order to tests their significance in explaining and predicting their impact in trade flows.

This research aims to document, measure and assess five hypothetical implementations of blockchain technology in trade finance and customs worldwide, focusing on LAC region. To this end, the study proposes a three-step framework. First, it will follow a theoretical review of the Gravity Model and Blockchain technology applied in trade. The next step will provide an econometric model-based and the construction of proxy variables to evaluate hypotheses about the significance of five variables related to bilateral trade flows worldwide; consequently, the test is performed between LAC countries and all the countries of the world. Finally, the third step will analyze the results to determine whether Blockchain Technology boosts or not bilateral trade, and, based on the results, will provide suggestions about further studies.

The Gravity Model

Newton's gravitational theory states that the attraction between two planets is proportional to their masses and inversely related to the distance between them. From this model application into economics, the Gravity Model of bilateral trade, in its most basic form, states that trade between two countries is proportional to the product of their masses (usually measured by their GDPs) and inversely related to the distance between them, which can be interpreted as well as the resistance factors that tend to diminish the gravity pull.

The Gravity Equation has been very successful in explaining actual trade patterns; in fact, it is considered to be "state of the art" for the determination of bilateral trade (Leamer & Levinsohn, 1995). The Gravity Model has caused an upsurge of thousands of publications and working papers covering a wide variety of regions, time periods, and sectors. For example, Disdier and Head in their meta-analysis of the effect of distance on trade cover 1,052 separate estimates in 78 papers (Disdier & Head, 2008). By linking trade flows directly with economic size and inversely with trade costs, usually proxied by geographical distance as an indicator of transport costs, the Gravity Model captures some deep regularities in the international trade and production pattern. Indeed, Leamer and Levinsohn have argued that the Gravity Model has produced "some of the clearest and most robust findings in empirical economics" (Leamer & Levinsohn, 1995).

The Gravity Model has been expanded by integrating, in addition to the production of countries and the distance between them various variables, the inclusion of factors such as population, changes in trade conditions and variables to control differences, in geographical or historical aspects (Dlamini, Edriss, Phiri, & Masuku, 2016), which seek to reflect those factors that have a significant influence on the commercial flow. Martinez-Zarzoso and Nowak-Lehman do not limit it to the distance and GDP, but also include variables such as population and other dummy variables that control for differences in historical ties, trade agreements, and geographic factors such as landlockedness³ (Martinez-Zarzoso & Nowak-Lehmann, 2003), common borders, common languages, etc. In general, it can be stated that the Gravity Model is an instrument that seeks to define bilateral trade as a function of the characteristics of the two economies involved, combining those elements, both favoring and disadvantaging commercial trade.

³ Landlocked definition, shut in completely, or almost completely, by land.

Multiple applications have been derived using the Gravity Model proving its capacity to extend the complexity decomposing trade costs into a tariff and non-tariff component (Head & Ries, 2001) (Jacks, Meissner, & Novy, 2008); and studying the effects of regional trade agreements (Krugman, 1991) (Frenkel, 1997) (Carballo, Graciano, Schaur, & Martincus, 2018). Several studies have attempted to analyze the effect of trade facilitation indicators on trade flows. Trade facilitation, as defined by the WTO (1998) basically refers to improving the logistics of moving goods across and its related procedures involving handling data and documentation required for the transportation of goods. For example, in the 2010 study of Felipe and Kumar, the authors found that improving trade facilitation in Central Asian countries will lead to an increase in bilateral trade flows (Felipe & Kumar, 2010). The study uses the World Bank's Logistic Performance Index (LPI) as a measure of trade facilitation and finds that infrastructure improvement, followed by logistics and efficiency of customs and other border agencies, enhances trade among the countries under study. Zhongxiu and Shahzad constructed an index of trade facilitation variables measured in terms of infrastructure, institution, transport services, efficiency of import and export procedures and transparency of border administration and found that an improvement in trade facilitation increase the import flow in Pakistan (Zhongxiu & Shahzad, 2020).

More recent developments of the Gravity Model include the cutting-edge work developed by Alleyne *et al.* where the authors analyze the effects of non-tariff barriers (NTBs) on trade volumes among the Caribbean countries (Allende Lopez, Alleyne, Giles Alvarez, Khadan, & Waithe, 2020). The base argument is that NTBs could be reduced by implementing distributed ledger technology (DLT), more specifically blockchain-based technology. Besides confirming some of the classic variables of the Gravity Model, e.g., distance and culture, the study finds that bilateral exchange rates, transfer fees, and required documentation affects trade negatively. The paper constitutes one of the first of its kind to explore the potential benefits of using DLT such as blockchain ledgers in trade flows.

Introduction to Blockchain

Blockchain is a technology that first appeared in 2008 within the cryptography⁴ expert community. It was conceptualized by an as-of-yet unidentified individual or group of individuals under the alias "Satoshi Nakamoto" and first implemented in 2009 as a core component of the cryptocurrency Bitcoin⁵. While Blockchain and Bitcoin are historically linked, they are two different things. Blockchain is the technology underpinning Bitcoin; it is the virtual infrastructure that Bitcoin uses. Bitcoin is a cryptocurrency, but the term is often used to refer to the cryptocurrency and the protocol underlying it – i.e., Blockchain. This confusion may be one of the reasons why it took so long for people to realize that Blockchain can be used in areas other than for cryptocurrencies. The technical approach to Blockchain as a technology is out of the scope of this paper.

While Bitcoin was the first real-life application of Blockchain, Blockchain technology combines several underlying techniques that have existed for at least four decades. For the five years that followed the creation of Bitcoin, the history of Blockchain remained nearly synonymous with the history of Bitcoin. However, it was only from 2013 that blockchain technology started to make a name for itself due to its use in other cryptocurrencies, such as Ethereum, and more recently, beyond the financial technology (fintech) industry.

⁴ The concept of cryptographically secured chains of blocks was first described in 1991 by Haber and Stornetta (1991), but it was only in 2008-09 that the technology was effectively implemented.

⁵ A cryptocurrency is a digital currency that uses cryptography for security. See Nakamoto (2008).

Regarding trade costs, Blockchain has the potential to reduce an array of costs considerably, including data and documents consignment, logistics and transportation, coordination, processing, networking verification, exchange rate and financial intermediation costs; all this through the automation and digitalization of processes and transactions, increasing transparency and more importantly, the decentralization of data management across all parties. To the date of this research, it is difficult to find enough rigorous scientific information about the assessment of the reduction of trade costs under a Blockchain system, nonetheless, according to a WTO document, "preliminary indications at hand tend to point to a notable impact. Cost reduction estimates in the financial sector and the shipping industry range from 15 to 30 percent of total costs. According to the World Economic Forum, the removal of barriers due to Blockchain could result in more than US\$ 1 trillion of new trade in the next decade." ⁶

In order to understand how Blockchain could contribute to the facilitation of trade, it is helpful to understand why do these "procedures and required information flows" exist, which trade facilitation aims to "simplify, standardize and harmonize". The rationale generally is a lack of confidence. There are multiple reasons why governments have created procedures for controlling imports and exports. These include ensuring tax collection, health and citizens protection and ensuring that domestic producers are not subject to unfair competition - for example, from foreign companies that manufacture non-compliant products according to the domestic market. Likewise, governments sometimes try to limit imports to protect national producers from external competition - although this strategy can end up being counterproductive and damage national competitiveness.

Government procedures include controls because they don't trust companies will pay customs duties correct nor will they comply with all required regulations. In general, governments also distrust the validity of the documents and, especially, of the official certificates and other documents from imported goods' country of origin (there is fear of them being counterfeited, obtained in exchange for a bribery or, in the case of laboratory tests, issued by entities that are not qualified enough to do it).

Financial institutions turn to third parties to validate the creditworthiness of companies and have created procedures to reduce the risk of fraud and ensure that trade finance and credits granted to exporters are based on verified contracts and deliveries. They do it because they don't trust the trading operators are always honest about their client's financial situation or about submitting error-free documents (which may be related to fraud).

Trade operators, governments and financial institutions require that carriers follow procedures to prove that all goods have been delivered (no goods should disappear along the way) and everything should have arrived in perfect conditions to the importer facilities (particularly in the case of goods sensitive to time, temperature and other factors). Trade operators do this because they distrust each other (they fear shipments arrive incomplete); but also, they do not trust carriers not harming or stealing goods. Financial institutions, for their part, do not trust trade operators in shipping all products they have been paid for, or that they buy the 100% of the goods they agreed on being financed for, and they don't trust carriers either (for the same reasons that they don't trust trade operators). Importers and exporters sometimes hire third parties (inspection companies, banks, customs brokers and freight forwarders) to provide themselves with the services of control and coordination trading transactions. They do it to ensure the correct behavior of their business partners, government agencies and carriers (because they don't trust them) or to comply with procedures that have become extremely complex and difficult to understand. Or for both purposes. This "lack of confidence" that to some

⁶ (Ganne, 2018)

extent covers all commercial transactions, literally penetrates the very fabric of international trade, hence generates huge opportunities for technology Blockchain.

The financial impact of trade barriers due to lack of confidence, results in the accumulation of all costs and delays to which a product and its components are subject. This accumulated cost is further expanded due to the fact that the imported content in manufactured products that are exported is, on average, 25% or more (OECD, 2021). Consequently, the costs related to the imported components that are already included in the price of the product, are increased when this product is exported, and in turn, is subject to export and import procedures and costs. These costs rooted in time and work efficiency, are addressed in this research as performance-related factors.

Performance is accomplishment, and when it coincides with efficient use of time, it equals optimal results with minimum costs. This research makes an emphasis on performance and efficiency on trade procedures in which Blockchain offers relevant and highly potential solutions. There are other factors related to performance and efficiency, for example, the availability of information; this comprises not just how accessible the information is, but also how complete it is. Lacking in either accessibility or completeness is not just an incremental factor of time required but also detrimental to results quality, meaning efficiency and performance become compromised, which translates in higher economic costs, which ultimately results in higher prices.

In each step of the long process of the average trade there several tens of roles involved between the seller and the buyer, it is a highly complex process made of a series of cumbersome transactions, in which every transaction has its own variable of performance and time efficiency as well as its own probabilities of making a mistake, thus increasing trading costs for reasons that can be proved to be avoidable. Confidence and information availability are closely related to performance and time efficiency; these are essential concepts put into practice through a system that can offer a viable solution to avoidable specific causes of trade barriers (non-trade barriers). Blockchain offers an array of solutions in multiple levels relevant to the issues at hand.

Proposed Variables for the Model and their Premise

The panorama of international trade has numerous opportunities for improvement, since the current processes are linked to old technologies and procedures that might no longer have advantages. Non-tariff trade barriers are associated with lower trade volumes and recent policy discussions have focused on the use of Blockchain technology as an effective mechanism for reducing non-tariff trade barriers (Allende Lopez, Alleyne, Giles Alvarez, Khadan, & Waithe, 2020). From trade finance to transportations and logistics, customs, insurance, intellectual property, distribution, digital identity and government procurement, possible applications of Blockchain cover a diverse set of areas related to international trade.

The general applications of Blockchain to international trade are broad, including setting up a multilayered system in which multiple stakeholders could operate and have interoperability with other entities and government agencies such as customs, offering in-real-time operation, management, submission and issuing of documents, with an unprecedented level of security. Once the implementation phase is over and is extendedly used across the trading process from exporter to importer, the results are expected to be a game-changer for trade, consequently facilitating trade which translates directly to an increase in volume of trade. It has the potential to reach the point in which it could help trade move closer to becoming paperless.

Regarding non-tariff trade barriers, the Doing Business Project of World Bank provides an extensive array of indicators, including some highly relevant to trade facilitation and non-tariff trade barriers. The focus of this paper is on non-tariff-related factors expressed by trade facilitation variables that could be enhanced by the implementation of Blockchain technology. This is confirmed in multiple whitepapers and research papers, from which one from OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) stood out for this research. The OECD paper (2013)⁷ states that most significant trade facilitation measures (i.e., those that have the highest effect on trade volumes) are simplification of documents, harmonization of documents, information availability, automated processes and streamlining of border procedures (Moise & Sorescu, 2013). From these OECD results, this research proposes the following set of five variables, named by the author of this paper as Blockchain Benefit Variable or BBV, which were selected as the result of extensive research in publicly available publications on trade facilitation indicators.

BBV1 is a score (0-8) that measures the depth of credit information index of country *i*

BBV2 represents credit registry coverage (% of adults) of country *i*

BBV3 represents credit bureau coverage (% of adults) of country *i*

These variables represent the performance of three key aspects of trade finance. BBV1 represents the depth of credit information which measures rules and practices affecting the coverage, scope and accessibility of credit information available through either a credit bureau, credit registry or both^{8,9}. BBV2 reports the number of individuals and firms listed in a credit registry's database (those managed by the public sector), with information on their borrowing history within the past five years. BBV3 reports the number of individuals and firms listed in a credit bureau's database (private firm or nonprofit organization), with information on their borrowing history within the past five years, plus the number of individuals and firms that have had no borrowing history in the past five years. These three variables represent two fundamental factors in trade finance: depth comprehends the quality and completeness of credit-related information of the people in credit databases, and coverage comprehends the percentage of people inside credit databases. These factors reflect a country's credit database's performance which is essential in providing trade finance.

How is credit information related to Blockchain technology? One of the main issues in this specific field is lenders having credit information on investors seeking for credit. The answer to this issue involves information availability which fundamentally relies on coverage. Blockchain offers a system in which loan seekers are able to not only have certified verifiable digital identity, but also to be in a database which could be easily accessed by lenders and offer their finance solutions in a prompt and trustworthy manner. In theory, the identities would be backed up by the countries' government compelling organism, thus providing legitimacy. This technology has the potential to facilitate the accessibility to trustworthy and complete information in a more inclusive way, providing a unified and interconnected trade finance system that can be fed information by everyone, verified by the compelling authorities, inquired by lenders and approved by banks. Furthermore, this database will be managed in real time thus minimizing risks of false information, outdated data or delays caused by the communication between entities. In the words of the WEF (2019): "it removes inefficiencies from existing processes and improves assessment, minimizing human errors in documentation, checks,

⁷ <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5k4bw6kg6ws2-en>

⁸ A credit bureau is defined as a private firm or nonprofit organization that maintains a database on the creditworthiness of borrowers (individuals or firms) in the financial system and facilitates the exchange of credit information among creditors.

⁹ A credit registry is defined as a database managed by the public sector, usually by the central bank or the superintendent of banks, that collects information on the creditworthiness of borrowers (individuals or firms) in the financial system and facilitates the exchange of credit information among banks and other regulated financial institutions.

instant verification and reconciliation of records, automatic execution of workflow steps, and instant and secure exchange of data"¹⁰ (Warren, Wolff, & Hewett, 2009). Following, under a more specific scope, some functions and relations are elaborated.

As it was previously explained in the Blockchain section, credit information availability plays a key role in trade finance, and trade finance is a fundamental part of international trading. Worldwide, 27% of firms identify access to finance as a major constraint¹¹ while about 70% of formal SMEs in developing countries are estimated to be either unserved or underserved by the formal financial sector (Stein, Ardic, & Hommes, 2013). Credit registries and bureaus are fundamental parts of the financial infrastructure that supports the solutions of access to financial services, including credit. By sharing credit information, they help to reduce information asymmetries, increase access to credit for small firms, lower interest rates, improve borrower discipline and support bank supervision and credit risk monitoring (World Bank Group, 2022).

Traditionally banks and lenders endorse loans based on a system of credit reporting. Blockchain technology proposes peer-to-peer (P2P) loans. The latter are complex programmed loans that can simulate a syndicated or mortgage loan structure, moreover a faster and safer loan process in general. Generally, in order for a bank to grant a loan, the bank has to assess the risk by revising factors like credit score and other relevant information about the client. To obtain this information, it has to request this data to credit bureaus (private entities) (e.g. Experian, Equifax). The concentration of this sensitive information poses a risk of vulnerability¹². Instead, Blockchain technology offers a less expensive, more efficient and safer way of managing loans to a broader pool of clients. Having advantages as cryptography security, decentralized registry of historical payments, clients could be granted loans based on a global credit score, meaning the information would be more homogenous, complete and accessible to the client himself.

Traditionally, banks can spend up to three months performing Know Your Customer (KYC) procedures to verify that the information is in order. This includes verification of photo IDs, documents such as address proofs and biometrics. This time and efforts take a significant part in the costs. In addition to time and effort, completing KYC requirements also costs significant money. All this indirectly transfers to trade costs.

Blockchain technology has the capability of reducing the effort, time and money costs required in KYC compliance. By hosting all KYC client information on a blockchain platform, the decentralized aspect of the platform would allow the institutions that requests KYC access to that information. For instance, using this technology for KYC purposes could reduce personnel costs for banks by 10% (Goldman Sachs, 2017). Besides those administrative costs, Blockchain offers higher a cybersecurity and antifraud structure, by centralizing the storage of information, it requires more effort, time and computing power for a hacker to gain access to all the information of a client at once. Summarized, a Blockchain platform provides the capability to host and manage the information for credit databases and KYC compliance in an integrated and decentralized system.

BBV4 is the score (0-100) for the time for documentary compliance to import of country i.

BBV5 is the score (0-100) for the time for documentary compliance to export of country i.

¹⁰<https://www.weforum.org/whitepapers/inclusive-deployment-of-blockchain-for-supply-chains-part-1-introduction/>

¹¹ Enterprise Surveys database (<http://www.enterprisesurveys.org/>), World Bank.

¹² The September 2017 Equifax hack exposed the credit information of nearly 150M U.S.A citizens.

These two variables represent the performance and efficiency in handling the complying process of documentary requirements of government agencies of the origin economy, the destination economy and any transit economies. Documentary compliance should support an efficient movement of goods between ports. If not managed appropriately, documentation requirements can increase trade costs and reduce trade flows between countries. These variables measure the total burden of preparing the bundle of documents, transfer fees, office operations and government policies that will enable completion of the international product and partner pair. Introduction of Blockchain technology can improve the process of documentary compliance by providing a unified multilayered system in which all compelling entities participate, not just the country's customs, trade operators, exporters and importers, but also the adjacent governmental authorities that are responsible for specific inspections and certifications. Thus, the input of information would be almost immediately visible by every participant entity who requires to see and confirm it; modifications by the compelling entity could be done instantly and be verified in real time. Figuratively speaking it would be like having all the involved entities and parties virtually on the same table with all the documentation on the table, doing the submission, issuing, stamping and handling the rest of transactions in front of everyone else.

Regarding the importance of time performance in customs' documents and border compliance, it is directly related to international markets accessibility, thus plays an important role in an economy's development through trade. While tariffs are still among the policy instruments most widely-used to promote or restrict trade, their relative importance has declined (Hoekman & Nicita, 2011). Other factors, namely trade-related transaction costs, have taken precedence. Logistics and freight expenses, customs administrative fees and border costs have become more important for small traders. While the significance of small and medium-size enterprises (SMEs) in the overall economy is widely recognized, until recently SMEs were largely absent from trade debates. The World Trade Report 2016 focused on leveling the trading field for SMEs and concluded that, along with fixed entry costs, cumbersome border procedures and standards are major hurdles for SMEs (World Trade Organization, 2016). Given that SMEs account for the majority of firms and the vast majority of employment worldwide, encouraging government policies aimed at facilitating the participation of SMEs in trade is essential.

In many economies, inefficient processes, unnecessary bureaucracy and redundant procedures add to the time and costs for border and documentary compliance. Evidence from a study investigating delays in customs procedures shows that customs-driven delays have a significant negative impact on firms' foreign sales through a reduced number of shipments and buyers as well as exports per buyer (Djankov S. a., 2008). Another study using data on the days it takes to move standard cargo from the factory gate to the ship in 98 countries found that each additional day that a product is delayed prior to being shipped reduces trade by more than one percent (Djankov, Freund, & Pham, 2006).

Only recently has the relationship between administrative controls and trade volumes attracted the attention of multi-lateral trade networks. In 2013, for example, members of the World Trade Organization (WTO) concluded a Trade Facilitation Agreement (TFA) aimed at streamlining trade procedures. The TFA entered into force on February 22, 2017 upon the acceptance of the agreement by two-thirds of WTO members. The OECD estimates that fully implementing the WTO Trade Facilitation Agreement could reduce trade costs by 16.5% for low-income economies, 17.4% for lower-middle-income economies and 14.6% for upper-middle-income economies. Adopting even its simple (though often still costly) recommendations, such as automating trade and customs processes, could reduce costs for these income groups by 2.8–3.6% (OECD, 2018). A study by Carballo et al. finds that introducing new technologies, such as an electronic single window, that limit the number of interactions between firms and border agencies, is associated with both an increase in the number of firms and the volume of exports of user firms (Carballo, Graciano, Schaur, & Martincus, 2018).

Methodology & Data

The gravity equation that this study seeks to estimate follows closely the model developed by Alleyne *et al.* (2020) by estimating a panel regression gravity model for all world countries between 2015 and 2019. A subsequent regression was also conducted with a focus on LAC bilateral trade with rest of the world countries. The analysis aims to quantify the impact of NTBs in the form of trade facilitation variables, specifically those relevant to Blockchain Technology benefits, presented in a previous section, on the volume of trade between two pair of countries. Specifying from the general form of the gravity model and adjusting to include the specific set of NTBs variables proposed by this paper, namely BBV (Blockchain Benefit Variables), the following variation of this study's model equation has taken an the following augmented form:

$$\ln(T_{ij}) = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln(GDP_i * GDP_j) + \beta_2 \ln(D_{ij}) + \beta_3 \ln(COMLANG_{ij}) + \beta_4 \ln(COMREL_{ij}) + \beta_5 \ln(COLINK_{ij}) + \beta_6 \ln(BBV1) + \beta_7 \ln(BBV2) + \beta_8 \ln(BBV3) + \beta_9 \ln(BBV4) + \beta_{10} \ln(BBV5) + \log u_{ij}$$

T_{ij} is the bilateral trade volume (exports + imports) between countries i and j

$GDP_i * GDP_j$ is the product of country i 's and country j 's GDPs

D_{ij} represents trade costs between the two countries and captured as the geographical distance between them

$COMLANG_{ij}$ is a dummy variable and will be equal to 1 when countries i and j share a common language and 0 otherwise

$COMREL$ is a dummy variable and will be equal to 1 when countries i and j share a common religion and 0 otherwise

$COLINK_{ij}$ is a dummy variable and will be equal to 1 when countries i and j share a colonial past link and 0 otherwise

$BBV1$ is the score (0-8) of depth of credit information index of country i

$BBV2$ is credit registry coverage (% of adults) of country i

$BBV3$ is credit bureau coverage (% of adults) of country i

$BBV4$ is the score (0-100) for the time for documentary compliance to import of country i

$BBV5$ is the score (0-100) for the time for documentary compliance to export of country i

u_{ij} is a random error term. The α term is a regression constant, and the β terms are coefficients to be estimated.

The product of GDP serves as a proxy for the economic size for two countries in terms of production capacity and size of market. Larger countries usually imply a greater production volume, which in turn provides them with the capacity to increase their exports based on their comparative advantage. They also own larger domestic markets which means they are able to afford more imports. Therefore, an increase in the product of the GDPs of the two countries is expected to increase bilateral trade volumes. Thus, it is expected the estimated coefficient of $\beta_1 > 0$.

The trade resistance variables such as distance, trade agreements and cultural unfamiliarity such as common language and colonial linkages will influence trade flows as they represent trade costs agents. Anderson and van Wincoop (2003) and Harrigan (2003) showed that trade volume will be larger between country pairs that are closer to each other. The distance coefficient is expected to have a negative impact on trade flows since greater distances tend to increase transportation costs (the time and logistics required for shipment and communication). This coefficient measures the effect of relative distances of countries; a decrease in the distance coefficient indicates that trade with geographically distant countries increases relative to trade with geographically closer countries, whereas an increase indicates that trade with closer countries increases faster than that with distant countries. It is anticipated the coefficient $\beta_2 < 0$, but its magnitude matters more. Cultural closeness is expected to increase trade; thus pairs of countries that share language, religion and colonial past are expected to have a positive impact on trade flows.

All the BBV variables serve as performance indicators of key parts of the process of trade which Blockchain technology aims to improve. BBV1 variable scores the depth of credit information benchmarks economies with respect to the regulatory best practice on the coverage, scope and accessibility of credit information available through credit reporting service providers. BBV2 variable measures the coverage of the credit registry's database (public entities). BBV3 variable measures the coverage of the credit bureau's database (private entities). BBV4 is a score of the measure for the time for documentary compliance to import benchmarks of country i with respect to the regulatory best practice on the time for documentary compliance to import; it assesses the time associated with compliance with the import documentary requirements of all government agencies of the origin economy, the destination economy and any transit economies. BBV5 is a score of the measure for the time for documentary compliance to export benchmarks of country i with respect to the regulatory best practice on the time for documentary compliance to export; it assesses the time associated with compliance with the export documentary requirements of all government agencies of the origin economy, the destination economy and any transit economies. BBV4 and BBV5 scores range from 0 to 100, where 0 represents the worst regulatory performance and 100 the best regulatory performance, and is computed based on the methodology in the DB16-20 studies¹³. It is anticipated the coefficient $\beta_{6-10} > 0$.

Estimation Technique

The nature of the data requires the use of panel regression techniques to be applied on the specified Gravity Model. Broad discussion on how to handle zero trade flows between two countries has been argued since the problem is not a trivial one. The problem arises when a gravity model takes logarithms and estimates its log-linear equation; since $\log(0)$ is not defined.

As mentioned by WTO (2012), there are three approaches to handling zero trade:

1. Dropping the observations with zero trade
2. Adding a small constant to the trade value before taking logarithms
3. Estimating the models in intervals

The first method should be utilized if the zeros are random missing data or random rounding errors i.e., the zeros are distributed randomly and do not offer informative value. But if zero trade is really zero trade or reflects rounding errors due to very small trade flows; dropping these zeros would lead to a loss of important information and inconsistent results. Empirical work has used different approaches. Standard OLS approach has been used when observations of zero trade have been dropped under the assumption that the zero trade are randomly distributed.

The application of either fixed effects model (FEM) or random effects model (REM) should be decided upon choosing which is the most appropriate panel data regression model (Alleyne & Lorde, 2014). To examine which model is the most appropriate, the study uses the Hausman test for examination between the FEM and the REM. The results of the

¹³ World Bank Doing business methodology expansion. <https://archive.doingbusiness.org/en/methodology>

Hausman tests the null hypothesis that there would be correlation between the bilateral trade effects and the explanatory variables. If the results of the Hausman reject the null hypothesis i.e., the coefficients are not correlated; the FEM estimator would be efficient.

Another estimation issue to take into account is the so-called multilateral resistance terms (MRTs). Bilateral trade costs between two countries are not only determined by the trade costs between these two countries but it is also affected by the average resistance caused by the trade costs faced relatively with the rest of its commercial partners. Since MRTs are not directly observable, estimation procedures require other methods to incorporate their effect into the estimations. Using country fixed effects for importers and exporters has been used as an approach to take MRTs into account (Rose & Van Wincoop, 2001) (Feenstra, 2004) (Baldwin & Taglioni, 2006).

Data Sample

The trade flows, GDP, geographic and cultural variables are extracted from CEPII Gravity Database (CEPII, 2021). Its data spans from 1948 to 2020 and includes 252 countries, some of which only exist for a shorter period of time. The term “country” includes territories that are not formally independent, as well as past territorial configurations of countries. The dataset is dynamic in the sense that it follows the ways in which countries have changed over time. It is “squared”, meaning that each country pair appears every year, even if one of the countries in the pair actually does not exist. Nevertheless, when either destination or origin country do not exist, variables are set to missing, and dummy variables allow the users to easily get rid of the concerned observations. From CEPII Gravity Database’s list of variables, only the following were used:

Variable name	Content	Level
iso3	ISO3 alphabetic code	Unilateral
dist	Distance between most populated city of each country (km)	Bilateral
comlang_off	1 if countries share common official or primary language	Bilateral
comcol	1 if countries share a common colonizer post 1945	Bilateral
comrelig	Religious proximity index	Bilateral
gdp	GDP (current thousands US\$)	Unilateral
trade_flow_comtrade_o	Trade flow as reported by the exporter (in thousands current US\$) (source:Comtrade)	Bilateral
trade_flow_comtrade_d	Trade flow as reported by the importer (in thousands current US\$) (source:Comtrade)	Bilateral

Table 1: CEPII Gravity Database: List of variables used.

Note on `tradeflow_comtrade_o` and `tradeflow_comtrade_d` variables: These variables represent the same trade flow between pair of countries although both entries were taken into account to consider any difference in the recording of the data by the countries through estimating the geometric mean of every pair. Moreover, despite being multiple sources for trade flow data, the data used comes from Comtrade, as a decision taken by the author based on the sources' coverage comparison across sources.

The final database was obtained by assembling data from additional sources. In particular, besides data produced by the CEPII, we use data from institutional sources such as the World Bank, the WTO and the IMF. It also includes data produced by a variety of researchers, which has been made publicly available.

Additionally, the set of five variables called BBV was added. These variables are grounded on the premise that administrative barriers toll on trade costs, and this latter has a well-known significant effect on trade volume. This thesis' proposed set of BBV variables represent the (current and publicly available) variables measuring performance in administrative aspects that are the most relevant to the objectives of Blockchain technology. These BBV variables are five: three indicators of credit coverage and information availability, and two indicators of time performance in customs' documents and border compliance. These five variables are the author's work, and were the result of the researcher's analysis and selection process from almost 200 construction variables used by the World Bank Doing Business Project, to create the Doing Business Indicators. The variables were constructed based on their relevance to Blockchain technology benefits comprehended previously in this research.

Variable	Content	Level
BBV1	Score (0-8) of depth of credit information index of country i	Unilateral
BBV2	Credit registry coverage (% of adults) of country i	Unilateral
BBV3	Credit bureau coverage (% of adults) of country i	Unilateral
BBV4	Score (0-100) for the time for documentary compliance to import of country i	Unilateral
BBV5	Score (0-100) for the time for documentary compliance to export of country i	Unilateral

Table 2: Author's proposed BBV variables

Hypotheses

The hypotheses tested in the model are derived from the literature and case analysis of the technology of Blockchain, for which the series of five variables were created, one variable for each hypothesis, to test the significance of these variables which represent potential benefits of Blockchain technology.

The three key proxies for information availability and coverage aspects related to potential Blockchain technology's benefits are:

Hypothesis 1: depth of credit information index (BBV1) boosts trade flow.

Hypothesis 2: credit registry coverage (BBV2) boosts trade flow.

Hypothesis 3: credit bureau coverage (BBV3) boosts trade flow.

This research's two key proxies for performance and efficiency aspects related to potential Blockchain technology benefits are:

Hypothesis 4: time efficiency for documentary compliance to import (BBV4) boosts trade flow.

Hypothesis 5: time efficiency for documentary compliance to export (BBV5) boosts trade flow.

Results

This section contains the results of two regressions. The first is the regression for the whole world bilateral trade to test the hypotheses globally, thus proving its general goodness-of-fit. The second is the regression for bilateral trade of LAC countries with all the world countries.

In the first regression, all hypotheses can not be rejected.

In the second regression, all but one hypothesis can not be rejected.

The Hausman test was employed to examine which model (fixed effect vs. random effect model) was more appropriate for the analysis. The result of Hausman test shows that the probability of chi2 is greater than 0.05 and therefore we reject the null hypothesis that the coefficients are not different. A fixed effect model is more appropriate than a random effect model.

Dependent variable: bilateral trade volume	FEM
GDP	1.124*** [0.0099]
Distance	-1.278 [0.0288]
Language	0.642*** [0.0951]
Colony	0.898*** [0.1228]
Religion	0.077** [0.0922]
BBV1	0.407** [0.1404]
BBV2	0.102*** [0.0167]

BBV3	0.101***
	[0.0223]
BBV4	0.089**
	[0.0575]
BBV5	1.011***
	[0.0910]
Const.	-28.738***
	[0.8320]
<hr/>	
N	12014
Adj. R-sq	0.7481
<hr/>	

Table 3: First regression: Effects on world’s bilateral trade.

Gravity regression results for the panel Fixed Effects Method.

Significance levels: * p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01. Std errors in brackets.

Table 3 shows the results from the estimation for all sample countries. The results of all variables except for common religion were statistically significant at the 1 percent level and had in most situations the expected sign, in line with the findings of previous studies. According to the results, the model specified within this study fits the data with an acceptable level of accuracy, explaining 74.8 percent of the variation in the countries’ bilateral trade.

The product of GDPs shows a positive relationship with the trade flow among country pairs. This implies that an increase in countries GDP is expected to boost bilateral trade, where a 1 percent increase in the product of the country’s GDP leads to a 1.124 percent increase in trade with its trading partner.

Distance has the anticipated negative sign and registers a coefficient of more than 1; therefore, it confirms the literature on the distance being an impediment to trade. The three cultural proxies, common language, common colonial past, and common religion, show a positive relationship with trade flows, confirming the literature on the positive effect sharing cultural aspects between trading partners plays a positive role. All the previous variables’ results are in concordance with the literature and are not part of this research scope; thus, discussing them further is out of this thesis’ relevance.

The three key proxies for information availability and coverage aspects related to potential Blockchain technology’s benefits show a positive and statistically significant effect, therefore:

Hypothesis 1: depth of credit information index (BBV1) boosts trade flow cannot be rejected.

Hypothesis 2: credit registry coverage (BBV2) boosts trade flow cannot be rejected.

Hypothesis 3: credit bureau coverage (BBV3) boosts trade flow cannot be rejected.

This research’s two key proxies for performance and efficiency aspects related to potential Blockchain technology benefits show a positive effect, therefore:

Hypothesis 4: time efficiency for documentary compliance to import (BBV4) cannot be rejected.

Hypothesis 5: time efficiency for documentary compliance to export (BBV5) cannot be rejected.

An increase in the accessibility to credit information by the respective participants in the market will tend to increase the credits that are given out. The increase in credits will, in part, turn into investments in companies involved in the international trade sector. The BBV1 variable results show that each 1 percent increase in the score of the depth of credit information index leads, on average, to a 0.407 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. This result confirms the importance of the practices affecting coverage, scope, and accessibility of credit information available to the credit bureau and credit registry.

The BBV2 variable results show that for each 1 percent increase in the score of credit registry coverage, on average, it leads to a 0.102 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. This result confirms the importance of governmental credit system coverage. The coverage of the private financial entities also contributes to the increase in trade flow in similar magnitude as governmental credit system coverage. The BBV3 variable results show that for each 1 percent increase in the score of credit bureau coverage, on average, it leads to a 0.101 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. Again, this result confirms the importance of the public and private financial entities' credit system coverage.

The BB4 variable result shows that for each 1 percent increase in the score of time efficiency for documentation compliance to import, on average, it leads to a 0.089 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. Reducing the time required to process the documentation for importing goods significantly affects trade flows positively.

The BB5 variable results show that for each 1 percent increase in the score of time efficiency for documentation compliance to export, on average, it leads to a 1.011 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. Reducing the time required to process the documentation for exporting goods seems to have the most significant positive impact on trade flows among the potential Blockchain technology effects.

Effects on bilateral trade between the LAC and the world countries

Dependent variable: bilateral trade volume	FEM
GDP	1.103*** [0.0178]
Distance	-1.792 [0.0728]
Language	0.626** [0.1411]
Religion	-0.267** [0.1584]

BBV1	0.554**
	[0.3241]
BBV2	0.683***
	[0.0771]
BBV3	-0.096***
	[0.0400]
BBV4	0.345***
	[0.0644]
BBV5	0.200**
	[0.1328]
Const.	-19.777***
	[1.7403]
<hr/>	
N	4241
Adj. R-sq	0.7156

Table 4: Bilateral trade estimation of LAC with the world countries.

Gravity regression results for the Fixed Effects Method.

Significance levels: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Std errors in brackets.

Table 4 shows the results from the estimation for LAC with the world countries. The results of all variables were statistically significant at the 1 or 5 percent level and had in most situations the expected sign, in line with the findings of previous studies, except for common religion, which unexpectedly shows a negative relation. According to the results, the model specified within this study fits the data with an acceptable level of accuracy, explaining 71.6 percent of the variation in the countries' bilateral trade.

The product of GDPs shows a positive relationship with the trade flow among country pairs. This implies that an increase in the country's GDP is expected to boost trade flow between that country and its trade partners; where a 1 percent increase in the product of the LAC country's GDP leads to a 1.103 percent increase in trade with its trading partner.

Distance has the anticipated negative sign and registers a coefficient of more than 1; therefore, it confirms the literature on the distance being an impediment to trade. Nevertheless, distance was not statistically significant. The cultural proxies, common language, and common religion show a positive and negative relationship with trade flows, respectively, confirming the literature on the positive effect of sharing a common language but an apparent negative effect from sharing the same religion. Unfortunately, the explanation for this unexpected result is out of this research focus. The previous variables' results (except for common religion) are in concordance with the literature and are not part of this research scope.

This research's two out of three key proxies for credit information availability and coverage aspects related to potential Blockchain technology's benefits show a positive and statistically significant effect; one showed a negative relation; therefore:

Hypothesis 1: depth of credit information index (BBV1) boosts trade flow cannot be rejected.

Hypothesis 2: credit registry coverage (BBV2) boosts trade flow cannot be rejected.

Hypothesis 3: credit bureau coverage (BBV3) boosts trade flow can be rejected.

This research's two key proxies for performance and efficiency aspects related to potential Blockchain technology benefits show a significant positive effect, therefore:

Hypothesis 4: time efficiency for documentary compliance to import (BBV4) cannot be rejected.

Hypothesis 5: time efficiency for documentary compliance to export (BBV5) cannot be rejected.

The BBV1 variable results show that each 1 percent increase in the score of the depth of credit information index leads, on average, to a 0.554 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. The BBV2 variable results show that 1 percent increase in the score of credit registry coverage, on average, leads to a 0.683 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. This result confirms the importance of the government's credit system coverage. The BBV3 variable results show that 1 percent increase in the score of credit bureau coverage, on average, leads to a 0.096 percent decrease in trade flow with the trade partner. This result challenges the hypothesis of the importance of private financial entities' credit system coverage.

The BB4 variable results show that 1 percent increase in the score of time efficiency for documentation compliance to import, on average, leads to a 0.345 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner. The BB5 variable results show that for each 1 percent increase in the score of time efficiency for documentation compliance to export, on average, it leads to a 0.2 percent increase in trade flow with the trade partner.

Bilateral trade between LAC and the world shows results that follow the general (first) regression trend, except for religion. The variable related to Blockchain showing the largest effect is the coverage of the credit registry's database (public entities). However, credit bureau coverage (private entities) shows challenging results, suggesting this aspect in LAC may not be beneficial or even detrimental to bilateral trade. Financial markets and access to credit in LAC requires further development which might have higher effect if potentiated by governmental entities first and then followed by the private sector.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Blockchain technology entails a promise that could improve performance and efficiency in one of the main categories of obstacles affecting Latin American and Caribbean countries when they try to participate in world trade. The panel regressions conducted in this research show that variables related to Blockchain Technology can stimulate trade flows by facilitating trade finance via improvement of credit information availability, coverage, and customs clearance.

Results conducted with all the countries involved showed that the time required to process the documentation for exporting goods has the most significant positive impact on trade flows among the potential Blockchain technology effects. Reducing and improving efficiency in documentation processes showed significant effect in improving trade flows

worldwide. Access to credit information and coverage (public and private) also has significant positive effect in improving world trade.

This study shows that improving the performance and efficiency of in-depth credit information and public credit registry coverage in Latin America and Caribbean countries has the potential of boosting trade flows with their trading partners worldwide. However, unexpectedly the results show the contrary for the private entities' credit bureau coverage, which effect is not consistent with the worldwide regression results nor explained in literature. Therefore, the author of this thesis suggests further research on this specific topic and proposes a hypothesis to be tested: In LAC, trade finance that relies on private credit bureaus hinders trade in relation to trade finance based on public credit entities.

Blockchain is bringing Latin America closer to the holy grail of world trade through the CADENA project: integration and chain automation of financial, logistical, and information chains that support business transactions. Most governments of LAC are already predisposed to try this technology (Allende Lopez, Alleyne, Giles Alvarez, Khadan, & Waithe, 2020).

However, the research results must be taken with caution, as the evidence of the benefits of Blockchain on trade flows is still nascent. This thesis contributes to this field, but the author reckons that data and evidence are incipient and unavailable to provide definitive conclusions. Nevertheless, the author hopes this research will motivate more interest and research in this area, particularly in LAC, to support governments and policymakers.

Based on the results, policy recommendations can be made to benefit substantially trade for Latin America and the Caribbean. The next step forward would be to conduct research with updated information once the regional authorities, such as the Interamerican Development Bank, provide sufficient data on projects related to Blockchain such as the CADENA project.

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